

Navigating Proximity: Human Comfort Levels with Quadruped Robots in Shared Spaces*

R. Erlebach, P. Rosen and S. Wischniewski

Abstract— Understanding the factors that influence perceived comfort in human-robot interaction (HRI) is critical for designing robotic systems that enhance user experience. This study investigates the effects of robot behavior and spatial layout on comfort, specifically whether these factors interact or contribute independently to user perception. Participants encountered a quadruped robot in a corridor under different behavioral conditions (moving, stopping, sitting) and corridor width (narrow, wide), and their comfort ratings were assessed using validated scales. Repeated measures ANOVAs revealed a significant main effect of robot behavior, with participants reporting greater comfort when the robot continued to move than when it stopped or sat. Additionally, a significant effect of aisle width was observed, with greater comfort reported in the wider aisle. However, there was no significant interaction effect, suggesting that these factors influence comfort independently. These findings highlight the importance of both robot behavior and environmental design in shaping positive user experiences in HRI. Future research should explore individual differences, such as attitudes toward quadruped robots, as well as additional environmental factors and related concepts to further optimize human-robot interactions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-robot interaction (HRI) is a key area of research with implications for workplace safety and ergonomics. As mobile robotic systems are increasingly integrated into industrial and construction environments, understanding human responses to these technologies is crucial. While previous research has extensively explored interactions with humanoids and industrial robots, little is known about encounters with mobile quadruped robots, particularly among individuals with no prior robot experience. However, their introduction into the workplace raises issues of acceptance and perceived safety. Understanding how these robots should behave to promote a sense of comfort and safety is essential for their successful integration.

Current quadruped robots are among others designed for industrial inspection and construction site surveillance due to their mobility and robustness. Unlike wheeled robots, quadruped robots are designed with four legs, allowing them to navigate uneven terrain, climb stairs and overcome obstacles such as rubble, making them ideal for construction sites. Their ruffed construction ensures they can withstand harsh environments, including impacts, while shock-absorbing features minimize damage during rough navigation. Equipped with advanced sensors such as, cameras or LIDAR, quadruped

robots can perform real-time inspections to detect structural weaknesses and safety hazards. Their autonomous navigation systems allow them to move independently, avoid obstacles and adapt to environmental changes. Due to their autonomy and flexibility, quadruped robots can be used independently on construction sites. As the robots are capable of performing tasks without the presence of their operator, there is a possibility that bystanders will encounter these robots on their construction site. In the role of a bystander, the human does not directly interact with the robot but shares the same place and at the same time aims at avoiding a possible collision [1]. In general, the increasing use of robots poses practical challenges because people generally perceive robots as members of an outgroup and, as studies have shown, segregation can lead to negative attitudes [2]. These negative attitudes often stem from fears of real threats, which are reinforced by highly autonomous robots [3][4].

Previous research has identified several key factors that influence human-robot interaction, particularly with regard to comfort and proximity in different contexts. One critical aspect is a robot's approach behavior, which significantly affects how comfortable people feel during interactions. Studies have shown that participants generally prefer frontal or lateral approaches as they feel more predictable and less intrusive compared to unexpected or abrupt movements [5]. In addition, maintaining an appropriate physical distance is critical to ensuring positive interactions. Most people prefer robots to stay within the boundaries of their social or personal space, avoiding overly close contact that could lead to discomfort or unease [6]. Beyond physical proximity, a robot's behavior also plays a role in shaping human perceptions and trust. The way a robot moves, reacts, and positions itself relative to a person can influence whether the interaction is perceived as safe and predictable. Research has shown that proximity and movement patterns contribute to building trust, as users tend to feel more comfortable when robots exhibit smooth, natural, and context-aware behaviors [7]. In addition, individual differences and prior experiences with technology, pets, or other robotic systems may influence a person's tolerance for close interactions with robots. Studies suggest that people who have experience with animals or robots may be more accepting of robotic proximity because they are already familiar with non-human agents in their personal space [8]. This highlights the importance of not only robot-specific factors, such as appearance and behavior, but also human-related factors, such as attitudes toward robots and previous

* The author(s) declare that they have received financial support for the research, writing, and/or publication of this article. This work is co-financed by project "Human Centered Technologies for a Safer and Greener European Construction Industry (HumanTech)", which received funding from the European Union's research and innovation program Horizon Europe (grant agreement N° 101058236).

All authors are with the Federal Institute of Occupational Health and Safety, 44149, Dortmund, Germany (corresponding author to provide e-mail: Erlebach.rebecca@baua.bund.de)

interactions with them. People's pre-existing perceptions and familiarity with robots can significantly influence how they react to encounters, especially in professional environments where robotic systems are increasingly integrated [9].

While these studies provide valuable insights into human preferences and behavior towards robots, many were focused primarily on humanoid or wheeled robots, which differ in mobility and interaction dynamics from modern quadruped designs. Given recent advances in mobile robotic systems, such as quadruped robots, it is important to revisit these findings in the context of contemporary robotic technologies. Current research on how quadruped robots, which mimic the appearance and movement of animals, are perceived in the real world is limited. This study aims to help fill this gap by providing updated empirical data on initial human responses to quadruped robots in workplace-like environments. By analyzing these interactions, the study aims to provide a deeper understanding of how different robot behaviors and spatial contexts influence human comfort during initial encounters.

This study investigates how the behavior of a quadruped robot influences comfort during first encounters in a controlled environment. Specifically, the research examines how variations in the robot's behavior and the width of the interaction corridor affect participants' experience. Participants were asked to rate their comfort using a series of validated questionnaires designed to measure different aspects of the interaction. This experimental approach aims to better understand the factors that contribute to human comfort when interacting with quadruped robots in the real world.

The results of this research will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on human-robot interaction and provide a foundation for future studies exploring the integration of robots in professional environments. In particular, these results will be useful in developing guidelines for designing and deploying mobile robots in a way that prioritizes worker comfort, safety and acceptance, ensuring that the integration of robotic systems into the workplace is both effective and well received.

II. STUDY DESIGN

A. Participants

Participants were recruited via a mailing list from BAuA's laboratory. All participants were between 18 and 65 years old ($M = 39.60$, $SD = 15.76$). A total of $N = 48$ participants took part in the study. All participants had no previous experience with robots in general. Sociodemographic data including age and gender were collected prior to the experiment. Of all participants, 52% ($n = 25$) reported to be female and 48% ($n = 23$) male.

One participant did not complete all trials and questionnaires and was therefore excluded from the analyses. All analyses are based on $N = 47$ participants.

B. Materials

The quadruped robot used was Boston Dynamic's Spot. Spot is an agile quadruped robot developed for autonomous navigation with a wide range of industrial applications. Spot is

capable of advanced mobility, allowing it to transverse a variety of terrains. It is also equipped with a suite of sensors and can follow pre-defined routes with remote control capabilities via a tablet interface. The robot used was equipped with a robotic arm, which was folded at all times during the experiment.

C. Experimental Design

The study used a 2x3 within-subjects design with two independent variables:

- Corridor width: 4 m (A1) vs. 2 m (A2)
- Robot behavior: stopping (B1), sitting (B2), continuing (B3)

This led to the following conditions:

TABLE 1: EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS.

		Robot Behavior		
		B1	B2	B3
Corridor width	A1	A1B1	A1B2	A1B3
	A2	A2B1	A2B2	A2B3

Each participant experienced all six conditions in a previously set order, which was the same for all participants. All conditions were repeated four times, resulting in a total of 24 trials per participant to enable habituation effects for all participants. The trials were therefore not randomized but set in a constant order.

Figure 1: Participant and robot meet in the 4 m condition. The robot displays different behaviors. On the left the robot is stopping until the participant passes, on the right the robot is sitting down until after the participant has passed.

The dependent variables measured were perceived comfort, perceived safety, and perceived threat as well as motion patterns.

D. Procedure

Participants were individually invited to a controlled experimental environment designed to resemble two workplace corridors, each 10 meters long and 4 meters and 2 meters wide (see figure 2). After providing informed consent,

they completed a brief questionnaire collecting sociodemographic data. They were then fitted with motion capture sensors (Movella XSens) to record their movements during their encounter with the quadruped robot. Next, participants were given an overview of the study, including a brief introduction to the robotic system they would be interacting with. After these explanations and safety instructions, they were guided to their designated starting positions. The robot's behavior was not revealed in advance to maintain a natural interaction. Once positioned, both the participant and the robot began to move simultaneously after a signal was given. The robot initiated its pre-programmed behavior when it detected the participant within a predefined range of 5.5 meters to ensure consistency across trials. To maintain controlled conditions, the robot moved only in straight lines based on preprogrammed paths. To increase safety, participants were instructed to walk along the right side of the corridor while the robot followed a parallel path along the right wall, minimizing the risk of collisions.

Figure 2: Experimental setup with two corridors. Left corridor is 4 m and right corridor is 2 m. The quadruped robot and the participant are shown in their starting positions across from each other.

After each encounter, participants rated their perceived comfort using a 7-point Likert scale (based on [10]) on computers located at each end of the corridors. The scale comprised of six items regarding the perceived comfort in the previous experienced conditions. All items were negative statements, meaning that a higher number signaled lower comfort and lower numbers showed greater comfort. All items were recoded prior to the analysis to improve understanding.

In addition to perceived comfort, perceived safety and perceived threat were also assessed. For perceived safety, the Questionnaire on Sense of Safety & Sense of Security [11] was used and for perceived threat, participants rated each interaction using the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) scale [12]. Moreover, each participant's movements were recorded using motion capture technology (Movella XSens). The focus

of this paper, however, is on perceived comfort and its implications for the use and deployment of quadruped robots.

E. Hypotheses

Based on the existing literature in HRI, the following research hypotheses are to be explored in this study.

- 1) Perceived comfort differs according to the robot's behavior (Stopping, sitting, continuing).
- 2) Perceived comfort increases with the width of the aisle.
- 3) Time (trial sequences) has an influence on the participants' perceived comfort ratings.
- 4) There are significant interaction effects between aisle width and robot behavior on perceived comfort.

F. Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using repeated measures ANOVA to examine the effects of corridor width and robot behavior on perceived comfort. Partial eta-squared (η^2) values were used to assess effect sizes, with thresholds of 0.01, 0.06, and 0.14 for small, medium, and large effects, respectively [13]. Post-hoc comparisons were performed when significant main effects or interactions were found. Effect sizes and confidence intervals were reported for all significant results.

III. RESULTS

The results show a significant main effect of behavior on perceived comfort, $F(2,82) = 9.49$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .19$, indicating that different robot behaviors influenced participants' comfort ratings. $\eta^2 = .19$ indicates a large effect. Pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction showed that there was no significant difference between stopping (B1) and sitting (B2, $p = .016$). However, there was a significant difference between continuing (B3) and both stopping (B1, $p < .001$) as well as sitting (B2, $p < .001$, see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Mean comfort scale ratings relating to robot behavior.

Additionally, a significant main effect of corridor width was observed, $F(1,41) = 8.40$, $p = .006$, $\eta^2 = .17$. Partial eta-squared showed a large effect size. Here, the pairwise comparison with Bonferroni correction showed a significant difference between the two conditions, with participants

reporting higher comfort in the wider corridor (A1) compared to the narrow corridor (A2, $p < .001$, see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Mean comfort scale ratings relating to corridor width.

The interaction effect between behavior and corridor width was not significant, $F(1, 890) = 0.08, p = .772, \eta^2 = .02$, suggesting that the influence of robot behavior on perceived comfort was consistent across different corridor widths.

In addition to behavior and corridor width, the trial number was used as another factor. A significant main effect was found for trial, $F(22, 890) = 6.36, p < .001, \eta^2 = .14$, indicating a large effect size. The results show that some habituation occurred and that participants became more comfortable over time.

Figure 5: Mean perceived comfort ratings across trials. Comfort scale was rated 1 to 7.

These results are summarized in table 2 and indicate that both robot behavior, available space, and trial number significantly influence perceived comfort. However, there is no combined effect of these factors. Participants felt most comfortable in the wider corridor and when the robot was continuing walking instead of stopping or sitting. For the stated hypotheses, this means that hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 are supported because there were significant main effects of both behavior and corridor width on comfort, while hypothesis 4 cannot be supported because there was no significant interaction effect found.

TABLE 2: REPEATED MEASURES ANALYSIS OF VARIANCES: EFFECTS OF ROBOT BEHAVIOR, CORRIDOR WIDTH ON COMFORT.

	Sum of Squares	df*	Mean Square	F
Robot Behavior	16.00	2	7.998	9.49**
Corridor width	4.417	1	4.417	8.40*
Trial number	27.38	22	1.25	6.36**
Behavior x Width	0.119	1	0.060	0.08

* df = Degrees of Freedom

** $p < .001$

* $p < .01$

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide important insights into the factors that influence perceived comfort in HRI with quadruped robots. A significant main effect of robot behavior on comfort was observed, with participants reporting greater comfort when the robot continued to move (B3) than when it stopped (B1) or sat (B2). This finding is consistent with previous research showing how motion-related factors, such as robot speed and motion patterns can significantly affect human comfort. Continuous robot motion can enhance human comfort, as it may be perceived as less intrusive or disruptive compared to stationary behaviors such as stopping or sitting. Much thought has been given in the different factors influencing perceived comfort in HRI, found, for example, in the Human Comfort Model [14] which highlights robot motion factors such as speed and human-robot proximity. Furthermore, the significant main effect of corridor width on comfort, with participants feeling more comfortable in the wider corridor (A1), is consistent with studies suggesting that physical space plays a crucial role in comfort in HRI [15, 16, 17]. Human comfort is a key determinant of collaboration quality, highlighting the importance of creating environments where participants feel comfortable [18]. In this study, a wider corridor likely provided a greater sense of spatial security, allowing participants to feel more comfortable and less threatened. Additionally, research on proxemics [19][20] provides further context for these findings. Mumm's work on human-robot proxemics shows that physical and psychological distance from robots is a key factor in determining comfort. Humans tend to keep a greater distance from robots that they perceive as more intrusive, which may explain why participants in this study felt more comfortable in the wider hallway. It has also been found that approach distances preferred in HRI are often comparable to those preferred in human-human interactions, suggesting that larger distances are generally perceived as more comfortable, especially when interacting with unfamiliar entities, such as robots [19]. Interestingly, the lack of a significant interaction effect between behavior and corridor width suggests that these factors independently influence comfort without a combined effect. This result is consistent with previous findings that suggested that robot motion factors are critical to human

comfort, but do not necessarily interact with environmental conditions [21].

Furthermore, the observation of a significant main effect of trial (repetition) on comfort suggests that participants' comfort was influenced by the trial sequence, with perceptions of comfort changing over the course of the experiment. This may reflect a habituation or acclimatization effect as participants became more familiar with the robot and the interaction context, potentially leading to less discomfort with repeated exposure. The finding is in line with previous research of habituation in HRI [5] and emphasizes the dynamic nature of comfort in HRI.

Negative attitudes toward robots have also been associated with lower perceptions of safety and comfort. It has been found that individuals with more negative attitudes toward robots felt less safe when interacting with them [8], which may further explain the variability in comfort levels observed in this study. Participants who were less comfortable with robots may have been more sensitive to their behavior, especially when the robot exhibited behaviors that were perceived as unpredictable or intrusive such as stopping or sitting.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate that both robot behavior and environmental factors, such as spatial layout, play a critical role in shaping perceived comfort during human-robot interactions. Participants reported greater comfort when the robot kept moving rather than stopping or sitting, highlighting the importance of predictable and fluid motion. In addition, wider aisles contributed to greater comfort, reinforcing the importance of spatial considerations in HRI design. The lack of an interaction effect between these factors suggests that they influence comfort independently, yet all remain essential to fostering a positive user experience. Furthermore, the significance of trial repetition underscores the importance of considering habitual effects in future HRI studies. Participants' comfort levels changed over the course of the trials, highlighting the potential for increased comfort with repeated interaction. Because there were no significant interactions found, it would be possible for future studies to take a closer look at the variables behavior and space without forcing habituation. Future studies can go in depth into singular factors to further improve our understanding of influences in HRI with quadruped robots.

The findings contribute to a broader understanding of HRI by highlighting the need for intentional design of robot behavior and thoughtful spatial planning. Future research could further investigate how individual differences, such as attitudes toward robots, affect comfort perceptions. In addition, exploring other contextual factors, such as environmental conditions or task complexity, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how to optimize human-robot interactions in different settings. In further research, related concepts of comfort, such as perceived safety or trust, may provide further insight into the impressions that participants gather when encountering quadruped robots for the first time. Further analysis of other assessed variables, such as perceived safety, perceived threat and movement patterns, collected using motion capture technology, is planned.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

*The author(s) declare that they have received financial support for the research, writing, and/or publication of this article. This work is co-financed by project "Human Centered Technologies for a Safer and Greener European Construction Industry (HumanTech)", which received funding from the European Union's research and innovation program Horizon Europe (grant agreement N° 101058236).

REFERENCES

- [1] Onnasch, L., Roesler, E. A Taxonomy to Structure and Analyze Human-Robot Interaction. *Int J of Soc Robotics* **13**, 833–849 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-020-00666-5>
- [2] Huang, H. L., Cheng, L. K., Sun, P. C., & et al. (2021). The effects of perceived identity threat and realistic threat on the negative attitudes and usage intentions toward hotel service robots: The moderating effect of the robot's anthropomorphism. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, *13*, 1599–1611. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-021-00752-2>
- [3] Chou, S.-J. (2018). The effects of anthropomorphism and autonomy of hotel service robots on consumer usage intention (Doctoral dissertation, Tatung University).
- [4] Zlotowski, J., Yogeewaran, K., & Bartneck, C. (2017). Can we control it? Autonomous robots threaten human identity, uniqueness, safety, and resources. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, *100*, 48–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2016.12.008>
- [5] Koay, K. L., Syrdal, D. S., Walters, M. L., & Dautenhahn, K. (2007). Living with Robots: Investigating the Habituation Effect in Participants' Preferences During a Longitudinal Human-Robot Interaction Study. *RO-MAN 2007 - The 16th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication*. Jeju, South Korea, IEEE.
- [6] Walters, M. L., Dautenhahn, K., Woods, S. N., Koay, K. L., Te Boekhorst, R., & Lee, D. (2006). Exploratory studies on social spaces between humans and a mechanical-looking robot. *Connection Science*, *18*(4), 429–439.
- [7] Hancock, P. A., Billings, D. R., Schaefer, K. E., Chen, J. Y. C., De Visser, E. J., & Parasuraman, R. (2011). A meta-analysis of factors affecting trust in human-robot interaction. *Human Factors*, *53*(5), 517–527. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720811417254>
- [8] Takayama, L.; Pantofaru, C. Influences on proxemic behaviors in human-robot interaction. In Proceedings of the IROS 2009, IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems, Louis, MO, USA, 11–15 October 2009; pp. 5495–5502. [Google Scholar]Kim & Mutlu, 2014
- [9] Khavas, A. (2021). Trust in human-robot interaction: An overview. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, *8*, 676648. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frobt.2021.676648>
- [10] Kim, Y., & Mutlu, B. (2014). How social distance shapes human-robot interaction. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, *72*(12), 783–795.
- [11] Akalin, N., Kristoffersson, A., Loutfi, A. (2019). Evaluating the Sense of Safety and Security in Human-Robot Interaction with Older People. In: Korn, O. (eds) Social Robots: Technological, Societal and Ethical Aspects of Human-Robot Interaction. Human-Computer Interaction Series. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-17107-0_12
- [12] Bradley, M. M., & Lang, P. J. (1994). Measuring emotion: The Self-Assessment Manikin and the semantic differential. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, *25*(1), 49–59. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7916\(94\)90063-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7916(94)90063-9)
- [13] Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203771587>
- [14] Wang, W.; Liu, N.; Li, R.; Chen, Y.; Jia, Y. HUCOM: A model for human comfort estimation in personalized human-robot collaboration. *Dyn. Syst. Control Conf.* 2018, 51906, V002T23A006. [Google Scholar]
- [15] Liu, L., Liu, Y., & Gao, X. Z. (2021). Impacts of Human Robot Proxemics on Human Concentration-Training Games with Humanoid

Robots. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*, 9(7), 894. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9070894>

- [16] Rubagotti, Matteo & Tusseyeva, Inara & Baltabayeva, Sara & Summers, Danna & Sandygulova, Anara. (2022). Perceived safety in physical human robot interaction—A survey. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*. 104047. 10.1016/j.robot.2022.104047.
- [17] Yamanaka, R. , Akiyama, T. , Blaquera, A. , Bollos, L. , Ito, H. , Kai, Y. , Yoshida, C. and Tanioka, T. (2024) Characteristics of Personal Space during Human-Robot Interactions: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Computer and Communications*, 12, 107-123. doi: [10.4236/jcc.2024.125008](https://doi.org/10.4236/jcc.2024.125008).
- [18] Stark, J.; Mota, R.; Sharlin, E. Personal space intrusion in human–robot collaboration. In *Proceedings of the Companion Of The 2018 ACM/IEEE International Conference On Human–Robot Interaction*, Chicago, IL, USA, 5–8 March 2018; pp. 245–246. [[Google Scholar](#)]
- [19] Mumm, J.; Mutlu, B. Human-robot proxemics: Physical and psychological distancing in human-robot interaction. In *Proceedings of the 6th international conference on Human-robot interaction*, Lausanne, Switzerland, 6–9 March 2011; pp. 331–338. [[Google Scholar](#)]
- [20] Walters, M.L.; Dautenhahn, K.; Te Boekhorst, R.; Koay, K.L.; Kaouri, C.; Woods, S.; Nehaniv, C.; Lee, D.; Werry, I. The influence of subjects' personality traits on personal spatial zones in a human-robot interaction experiment. In *Proceedings of the ROMAN 2005. IEEE International Workshop on Robot and Human Interactive Communication*, Nashville, TN, USA, 13–15 August 2005; pp. 347–352. [[Google Scholar](#)]
- [21] Lasota, P.; Shah, J. Analyzing the effects of human-aware motion planning on close-proximity human–robot collaboration. *Hum. Factors* 2015, 57, 21–33. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]